

TABLE-1 : PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF CHALCONE ANALOGUES
Ar'-CO-CH=CH-Ar

Ar'	Ar	Colour & crystal form	M.P.°C	Yield %	Time of reaction(hr.)	Halochromism conc.CH ₂ SO ₄	Diameter of zone of inhib. in mm.
1. 2'-OH-1'-naphthyl	2-OH-3-OCH ₃ Ph	ON	123	41	48	brown	—
2. 2'-OH-1'-naphthyl	3-OH-4-OCH ₃ Ph	LYN	109 (193)*	38	48	ruby-red	—
3. 2'-OH-1'-naphthyl	4-OCH ₃ Ph	RPr	158	53	36	purple	—
4. 2'-OH-1'-naphthyl	2-OAc	LYP	117	40	50	cherry-red	—
5. 2'-OH-1'-naphthyl	3-OAc ^f	LYG	121	35	50	dark orange	—
6. 2'-OH-1'-naphthyl	2-Cl	ON	139 (217)*	83	24	brown red	11
7. 2'-OH-1'-naphthyl	3-Cl	ORP	133	78	24	lemon yellow	10
8. 2'-Phenanthryl	2 OAc ^f	LYG	93d	40	50	orange	7
9. 2'-Phenanthryl	3 OC ₂ H ₅	YG	103	43	50	dirty yellow	—
10. 2'-Phenanthryl	2 : 3-(OCH ₃) ₂	YN	126 (207)*	60	36	yellow	—
11. 3'-Phenanthryl	2-Cl ^f	YN	122	83	24	cherry-red	11
12. 3'-Phenanthryl	3-NO ₂	YPr	178	65	20	red	10
13. 3'-Phenanthryl	4-OAc	YG	112d	56	48	brown	—

O = orange : Y = yellow : L = lemon : P = plate : Pr = prism : R = red : G = globules

N = needles *m.p. of 2,4-DNP

f = crystallised from benzene

The synthesis of chalcones achieved by Claisen-Schmidt condensation of appropriate methyl aryl ketones (0.005 mol.) and benzaldehydes (0.005 mol.) using saturated solution of sodium in methanol as condensing agent. One typical example is cited below.

An equimolar ethanolic solution of 3-acetyl phenanthrene and 2-chloro benzaldehyde was treated with Na/MeOH solution at 20-25° with constant stirring on a magnetic stirrer. The dark coloured reaction mixture (after 2 hr.) was kept at room temperature for 24 hr. The deposited compound was collected and the filtrate upon ice/HCl treatment gave a crude product which was crystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

Pharmacology :

The germicidal property was assayed by following agar-cup method using peptone, beef extract agar-agar as solid nutrient broth media. The bacteria selected for the screening were *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. The inhibition of growth was checked in a presterilized petridish after 24 hr. and results are recorded by measuring the diameter of zone of inhibition (Table 1).

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to authorities of H.B.T.I., Kanpur for providing necessary facilities, the Director, C.D.R.I., Lucknow for getting analyses and ir spectra. I also acknowledge the assistance of Mrs. Bimla Misra and Mr. Gokaran Nath Misra during the work and constant encouragement of Dr. Durga Nath Dhar, I.I.T., Kanpur.

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2-Hydroxy-1, 4-naphthalenedione (Lawson) A pH Indicator

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Manuscript received 13 February 1976, revised 5 August 1976, accepted 10 February, 1977

THE role of lawson as a chelating agent is well documented¹⁻⁷. Recently Sawhney and Trehan introduced juglone as a pH indicator⁸. However no mention has been made in literature regarding how the title compound behaves structurally under the influence of hydrogen ion concentration.

Experimental

All the reagents employed were of analytical grade. Baush and Lomb Spectronic 20, Spectrophotometer was used for absorption studies. Different sets containing varying hydrogen ion concentrations

NOTES

were prepared to get spectral absorption curves (Fig. 1) for lawsone. Each set consisted of 1ml (0.002M) of indicator and 5 ml of buffer solution. Volumetric experiments were performed by usual process using 1ml of indicator (0.348 g/litre in Et OH)

lawsone as an indicator in acidimetry. The relative error computed is 1.00 percentage.

Table 1 incorporates the precision results.

Absorption curves for lawsone at a series of pH, display that with the increasing pH, the absorption

TABLE-1

Titrate 10 ml (Na ₂ CO ₃ 0.1 N)	Titrant HCl (0.1 N)	No. of Titrations 10	Titre value 9.90	Relative error (%) 1.00	S.D.* 0.06
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* S. D stands for standard deviation

Fig 1. Spectral absorbance curves for 2-Hydroxy-1,4-naphthalenedione solutions at different pH values. One cm. cell thickness and 1 ml. of a solution containing 0.348g/litre idluted to 6 ml.

Results and Discussion

pH metric titrations, carried out in the presence of indicator, of carbonate solution with hydrochloric acid, reveal that the colour change (Orange red to Yellow) and stoichiometric point at the secondary stage of ionisation of carbonic acid. (pH (3.8) at equivalence point⁹) coincided. This experimental conclusion supported by colour change interval as pH ranging from 2.9 to 4.9, has led to suitably try

at wave length 450 nm, increases. The isosbestic point appears at 387 nm, confirming the presence of a system consisting of two chromophores. So the deepening of colour (Yellow to Orange Red) is due to structural change and not because of physical interaction between absorbing substance and its environments.

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